

Patient demographic	Name	
	Resident registration number	----- - * * * * *
	Phone	
	Medical history	<input type="checkbox"/> Diabetes <input type="checkbox"/> Hypertension <input type="checkbox"/> Hepatitis <input type="checkbox"/> Breast cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Other cancers
	Smoking	<input type="checkbox"/> Current smoker <input type="checkbox"/> Ex-smoker <input type="checkbox"/> Nonsmoker
Informed consent	<input type="checkbox"/> Agreed	

Hospital information	Hospital name	
	Business number	
	Surgeon name	
	Department	

Surgical characteristics		Operation date	---- / -- / --	
Laterality	<input type="checkbox"/> Left <input type="checkbox"/> Right <input type="checkbox"/> Both	Number of operation	<input type="checkbox"/> Primary <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary <input type="checkbox"/> Tertiary	
			<input type="checkbox"/> More than quaternary (reason):	
Surgery type	<input type="checkbox"/> Tissue expander	<input type="checkbox"/> Partial/Total mastectomy	<input type="checkbox"/> Immediate	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Delayed	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Other:		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Implant	<input type="checkbox"/> Partial/Total mastectomy	<input type="checkbox"/> Immediate (DTI)	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Delayed	
			(with tissue expander removal)	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Augmentation mammoplasty		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other:			
	<input type="checkbox"/> Tissue expander/ implant removal only			

Device characteristics	Manufacturer	
	Type of surface	
	Size	
	LOT No.	
	Serial No.	

Acellular dermal matrix information	Manufacturer	
	LOT No.	
	Serial No.	

Incision site	<input type="checkbox"/> Areolar
	<input type="checkbox"/> Axillary
	<input type="checkbox"/> Inframammary
	<input type="checkbox"/> Mastectomy scar
	<input type="checkbox"/> Mastopexy/Reduction scar
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other:

Explantation	<input type="checkbox"/> Device rupture	<input type="checkbox"/> Device malposition
	<input type="checkbox"/> Capsular contracture	<input type="checkbox"/> Breast Implant Illness
	<input type="checkbox"/> ALCL	<input type="checkbox"/> for ALCL diagnosis
	<input type="checkbox"/> Hematoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Seroma
	<input type="checkbox"/> Deep wound infection	<input type="checkbox"/> Mass
	<input type="checkbox"/> Patient wanted	<input type="checkbox"/> Other